

A Hospital-Based Retrospective Study on Sociodemographic Characteristics and Risk Factors of Diabetic Foot Ulcer

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetic ulcers are the most common foot injuries leading to lower extremity amputation.

Aim and Objectives: The present study was done to identify the sociodemographic characteristics and related risk factors in patients with diabetic foot ulcers.

Materials and Methods: This hospital-based retrospective study was conducted on adult patients with diabetic foot ulcers observed on their first visit to the Department of Surgery, Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri over a three-year period from October 2021 to September 2023. The sociodemographic characteristics and underlying risk factors data were collected from the included cases.

Results: A total of 137 patients presented with DFU among which majority of patients were male 98 (71.5%). Out of total cases, 64 (46.7%) DFU patients had diabetes for more than five years. Poor glycemic control was found in 109 (79.6%) of the patients. Footwear and loss of preventive foot were the most common precipitating factors. Most common site of DFU was fore foot (non-plantar 73%).

Conclusions: Advanced age, duration of diabetes, and poor glycemic control are associated risk factors for developing foot ulcers. Implementing organized screening programs for diabetic foot neuropathy and promoting awareness can help address these complications.

Keywords: Diabetic foot ulcers; Infections; Antibiotics; Diabetes.

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Introduction

India is emerging as the diabetic capital of the world, with 69.2 million people with diabetes (PWD) in 2015, with a prevalence rate of 8.8% and a projected 123.5 million cases in 2040 [1]. Uncontrolled diabetes leads to various complications, including peripheral neuropathy resulting in foot ulcerations, nephropathy and retinopathy [2]. Diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is one of the leading reasons for hospitalization among PWD [3].

Diabetic foot ulcer can be defined as an ulceration and /or destruction of deeper tissues associated with peripheral neurologic abnormalities and vascular diseases accompanied by infections [4]. Mechanism of ulcer is very complex and is associated with many factors which can be categorized into 3 groups: pathophysiologic changes, Anatomic deformities and environmental influences [5]. Pathophysiologic changes leads to peripheral sensory neuropathy and autonomic deficits [6]. Peripheral vascular diseases and

compromised immune system that reduces the wound healing capability. The anatomic deformities are consequences of motor neuropathy and charcots neuroarthropathy. Environmental factors like infection, acute and chronic trauma often acts as a precursor of ulceration.

Globally, the prevalence of DFUs is 6.3% within PWD, of which males (4.5%) constitute a higher proportion [7]. In developing countries, lack of public education on diabetes and lower socioeconomic status contribute to ignorance of diabetic ulcers, ultimately leading to major lower limb amputations.

A systematic review in India found that around 25% of PWD were diagnosed with DFU. Among those, 50% required hospitalization due to further infection, and 20% needed amputation [8].

An increase in DFU and its related amputations causes an additional burden to the patient and the healthcare system. It also affects the quality of life

of a patient and inflicts an economic burden on the patient and family [9].

Diabetic foot ulcer treatment is time-consuming and demanding. Fortunately, however, the occurrence of foot ulcers is preventable. Prior studies have stated that early detection of patients at risk of foot ulcers and management of risk factors could avoid amputations and foot ulcerations. Therefore, prediction of risk factors in patients with DFU facilitates disease management for clinicians to select the best strategy [10]. Unfortunately, there are few significant cohort studies on DFU incidence [11]. In India, few studies have been conducted on DFU incidence and risk factors. Additionally, socio-economic differences among different populations may have an effect on the incidence rates. So we aimed to evaluate DFU incidence and its risk factors. The present study will help to policy-makers in the region make practical and effective decisions based on the obtained outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This hospital-based retrospective study was conducted on adult patients with diabetic foot ulcers observed on their first visit to the Department of Surgery, Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri over a three-year period from October 2021 to September 2023.

Inclusion: We included all the patients with DFU of age 18 and above.

A DFU was defined as 'an infection, ulceration or destruction of deep tissues associated with

neurological abnormalities and various degrees of peripheral vascular diseases in the lower limb' [12].

We prepared a checklist which was completed by all participants. It included information about sex, age, blood pressure (BP), educational attainment, marital status, body mass index (BMI), smoking status, type of diabetes, diabetes duration, diabetes treatment type (oral anti-diabetes agents or insulin consumption), diabetic nephropathy, diabetic retinopathy, history of DFU or amputation, availability of preventive foot care, patient training about their feet, nail care, and ill-fitting shoes. We considered glycemic control using yearly average values of glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1c) and fasting plasma glucose (FPG) as independent variables. Based on average HbA1c values, diabetes control was further categorized as optimum (HbA1c \leq 7%) and poor (HbA1c $>$ 7%) [13].

We used Microsoft Excel 2007 to analyze the data. Continuous variables were described as mean \pm SD, and frequency and percentage were used to describe categorical data.

Results

During our study period, a total of 137 patients presented with DFU among which majority of patients were male 98(71.5%). Eighty (60%) of cases were found at age $>$ 60 years. In this study, most of patients with DFU were below property line and illiterate. There were 32(23.4%) obese cases. Baseline demographic characteristics of patients with diabetic foot ulcer are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of patients with DFU.

Sociodemographic Variables		Numbers (N=137)	%
Sex	Male	98	71.5
	Female	39	28.5
Age	18-40	5	3.6
	41-60	49	35.8
	$>$ 61	83	60.6
Socioeconomic Status	APL	68	49.6
	BPL	83	60.6
Educational status	Literate	63	46.0
	Illiterate	74	54.0
Body Mass Index (Kg/m ²)	18.5-25	42	31.0
	25-30	63	46.0
	$>$ 30	32	23.4
Smoking Habits	Current smoker	52	38
	Ex-smoker	15	11
	Non-smoker	70	51
Alcohol consumption	Yes	95	69

Out of total cases, 64 (46.7%) DFU patients had diabetes for more than five years. Poor glycemic control was found in 109 (79.6%) of the patients (Table 2).

Table 2: Risk Factor (underlying co-morbidities) of patient with DFU.

Underlying co-morbidities of DFU		Number (N=137)	%
Type of Diabetes	Type I or Other	7	5.1
	Type II	130	94.9
Duration of Diabetes	≥5 years	64	46.7
	≤5 years	73	53.3
Glycated hemoglobin (HBA1c	Optimum standard (<7%)	28	20.4
	Poor control (>7%)	109	79.6
Under Insulin Treatment		76	55.5
Hypertension		28	20.4
Dyslipidemia		121	88.3
Under statin treatment		83	60.6
Nephropathy		33	24.1
Retinopathy		67	48.9
Cerebrovascular disease		29	21.2
Ischemic heart disease		2	1.5

Footwear and loss of preventive foot were the most common precipitating factors. Most common site of DFU was fore foot (non-plantar 73%) (Table 3).

Table 3. Clinical presentation of patient with DFU.

Clinical presentation		Numbers (N=137)	%
Type of DFU	Neuropathic	57	78.1
	Neuro-ischemic	80	109.6
Precipitating Factor	Shoes	44	60.1
	Trauma	29	39.4
	Burn	5	6.8
	Pressure	3	4.5
	Other	12	16.9
	Unknown	44	60.1
	Anatomical Location of DFU	Fore Foot	101
Mid Foot or Above		36	26.3
Surface of DFU	Plantar	26	19.0
	Non-Plantar	111	81.0
Lateralization of DFU	Right	74	54.0
	Left	59	43.1
	Both	4	2.9

Discussion

Studies have reported higher vulnerability among males. Further risk enhances among those with a history of smoking and alcoholism [14,15]. In a similar line, the present study reported that 71% of DFUs were male. In the Indian scenario, males are the prime earners in most families and are mostly involved in outdoor activities than females. So, they are more prone to leg injuries (eg. trivial

trauma due to bare footedness) and hence more vulnerable to diabetic foot related problems.

The results revealed by the current study are in accordance with other studies, as most patients were in the age group of 60–79 years [16]. However, no difference was seen in the mean age of the patients of either sex.

Studies conducted in Thailand and India have shown a significant association between older age and DFU [17,18]. The longer duration of diabetes was significantly associated with the increasing risk of DFU (OR 1.488) [Table 3]. Studies performed in Jordan and China also highlighted the association of increased duration of diabetes [15,19].

A study found that poor glycemic level (HbA1c >7%) was seen to have a crucial impact on the risk factor of DFU. In that study, the binary logistic regression has shown a significant relationship between higher glycemic levels and the risk of amputation. Compared to optimum control glycemic level (HbA1c ≤7%), poor control glycemic level (HbA1c >7%) patients had a 1.439 times higher risk for DFU when adjusted to other confounding factors [20].

Uncontrolled glucose level increases the severity of the ulcer. Studies have reported issues in wound healing delays and more extended hospitalization due to poor glycemic control [21]. The development of neuropathy can be controlled significantly by maintaining glycemic levels at normal levels [22].

Frequent screening of glycemic levels can help patients and treating doctors detect complications in the early stage [23]. The Indian scenario of seeking diabetic foot help is much more different than that of Western countries. In India, delays are often evident in the standard treatment guidelines. These delays are mainly because of factors like accessibility, affordability, lower awareness and poor knowledge about the consequences of untreated conditions [24]. In developing countries, such delays pertaining to appropriate care for chronic conditions like DFU are high, which may further lead to exponential growth in the overall treatment costs [25].

The contribution of obesity to the risk of DFU is questionable. There are studies revealing that it is associated with DFUs, while other studies show that BMI has no significant correlation [26]. The analysis revealed that patients with DFU had higher BMIs (>25 kg/m²), and the DFU prevalence was higher in type 2 diabetes mellitus than in type 1 diabetes mellitus patients, which was consistent with the results of previous studies, but the mechanisms explaining it were not completely elucidated [27].

In a study conducted by Ramsey et al hypertension was present in 56.4% cases, ischemic heart disease was present in 07% cases and eye diseases in 23% cases [28]. This establishes association or aetiological relationship of diabetic foot with macrovascular complication and eye changes. In our study nephropathy was present in 12 (24%) cases. This was a well-known risk factor reported in earlier studies [29].

Different risk factors contributing to DFU development have been reported in separate studies [30]. However, some factors are more frequently cited in different studies. A study analyzed the data in univariate and multivariable logistic regression models. The final DFU risk factors in that study were: a history of previous DFU or amputation, ill-fitting footwear, smoking, loss of preventive foot care, and decreased physical activity [31].

Patients with a history of DFU or amputation may be prone to several micro- and macro-vascular complications such as diabetic neuropathy and ischemia, which may explain the higher threat of subsequent ulcers. In a meta-analysis conducted in 2018, previous history of DFU had the highest odds of ulcer development among all other independent risk factors [OR = 6.59(95% CI: 2.49, 17.45) [32]. Nevertheless, in a prospective cohort study in Tanzania, history of DFU or amputation was significantly related to ulcer development only based on univariate analysis, but it did not remain in the model after multivariable logistic regression [33].

Properly fitting footwear is an essential element in preventing DFU by lowering inflammation and callus formation. The exact number of ulcers initiated with unsuitable footwear (material or condition) is unknown. However, according a previous study, 40% of ulcers appeared at the hallux, 13% on the dorsum of digits, and 10% on the plantar side of digits. These are possible sites that may be affected by footwear abrasion, which will lead to ulcer development. External traumas are described as factors frequently contributing to DFU. Minor trauma can be ill-fitting footwear wherein the soft tissues of the foot remain weight-bearing for a long time [34].

After adjustment for other variables in this study, smokers had 3.87 times higher odds of developing DFU in comparison to non-smokers. This gives the impression that there may be an association between smoking and the male gender in the assessed population since male gender was correlated significantly with DFU in multivariable analysis in the first phase of ADFC, and smoking was excluded after backward elimination. Additionally, in this phase, smoking was superior to gender, and only smoking remained in the model while gender was excluded. It should be noted that in the Iranian culture, most smokers are men, which may clarify why only one of these two variables (smoking and male gender) remained in the regression model ultimately. In a retrospective study in Albania in 2021, smoking remained significant in multivariable analysis, which is consistent with our results [35]. Furthermore, in Alberta's Caring for Diabetes (ABCD) study, smoking was reported as a predictive factor for DFU development [36]. A systematic review and

meta-analysis suggested that smoking had a damaging influence on the healing of DFU [37]. On the contrary, in Tanzania prospective cohort study, smoking was a predisposing factor of DFU only in univariate analysis but not in the multivariate investigation [33]. In Bin Hameed's study, smoking had no significant contribution to DFU occurrence [38].

Conclusion

Advanced age, duration of diabetes, and poor glycemic control are associated risk factors for developing foot ulcers. Implementing organized screening programs for diabetic foot neuropathy and promoting awareness can help address these complications. Further research is needed to determine the effectiveness of diabetic foot prevention programs in reducing amputations and related hospitalizations. Knowing the etiology and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of these isolates is crucial for planning appropriate treatment options for patients. This includes selecting the most effective antimicrobial therapy, achieving good glycemic control, and implementing proper foot care.

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